

GAMIFICATION MODULE SCRIPT AND SURVEY

Below, both the script (1) and assessment questions (2) related to the Smart2B gamification module which will be presented to the (future) workshops' attendees (i.e., Smart2B users/actors) can be found. The script consists in a walk-through tutorial for the gamification module of the Smart2B application, where users are guided through the different sections of the games tab, within the UI – the gamification module. The questions consist in three linear numeric scale questions and one open-ended question, assessing the user-friendliness, interaction and de adequacy to the user needs.

1. Consult the Games module

On the UI dashboards travel to the Games tab, where you'll be able to join the Smart2B's gamified component. For test purposes, the values which will be presented see are mere examples. Try out the gamified module section for no longer than 5 minutes and move through the script. Located in the top left of each page there's a backward button which you can use to move between pages, directing you to the gamification module home page.

1.1. On the introductory hero page choose a unique nickname (4 to 12 characters). If when traveling to the Games tab you are not presented with an introductory page and you are not prompted to insert a nickname you can choose another of the buildings, the user is associated with. Hint: click on the most top-left button in the application.

1.2. After choosing a unique name your are directed to the gamification module homepage. Interact with the buttons and elements. Check how many XP points you have and how much energy you have accumulated in your virtual battery with your daily streak.

1.3. Travel to the challenges section, by clicking in the respective button. On the challenges page check the different challenges: the monthly and weekly mission, and the 4 weekly

challenges. Check if the average daily consumption is bigger or smaller than the daily consumption target.

1.4. Travel to the leaderboards section. Check on which place are you on the different Smart2 competitions.

1.5. Travel to the progress page and check how much XP do you require to reach the next level and how many levels would it take for you to reach the next stage.

1.6. Travel to the Advisor section. Check the latest SRI assessment of your building and the smart advice provided by the SPA&A service.

2. Questions concerning the Gamification component (Games tab).

Please, answer the following questions:

2.1. The several elements found within the Gamification component (point system and how can you accumulate more points, competitions and leaderboards, challenges, etc) and its rules-of-play are clear to the user?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Totally Disagree Totally Agree

2.2. The gamification component functionalities are user-friendly?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Totally Disagree Totally Agree

2.3. Users can easily travel through the gamification module pages and identify the displayed information:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Very Hard Very Easy

2.4. Do you have any suggestions to improve the Gamification module? (ex. overall design suggestions, an alternative for the “Games” tab name or even new content to include in the Smart2B challenges, or some complementary comments regarding the questions above).